

STUDY OF CHEMICALS IN ALLIUM MOTOR PLANT BY EXTRACTION METHOD

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Abstract: This article discusses the use of medicinal plants currently in development and their composition. Study of vitamins contained in Allium motor plant using chemical methods. Vitamin analysis was carried out using a 0.5% solution of acetic acid as the mobile phase in phase A and acetonitrile in phase B in alternating mode. Chromatogram analyses of vitamins B1, B2, B6, B9, B12, C and PP contained in Allium motor plant were carried out from standard samples.

Keywords: Allium motor, extraction, vitamins, natural, medicinal plants.

Introduction

Modern socio-economic changes in the world community and in Uzbekistan require changes in the education system at all levels. They are related to the goals, content, and results of the educational process, increasingly clearly orienting future specialists to independence, competitiveness, creative initiative, and mobility, which is reflected in the state educational standards for all levels of education.

In recent years, the republic has been implementing consistent reforms in the protection of medicinal plants, rational use of natural resources, the organization of plantations for the cultivation and processing of medicinal plants, and their processing. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-251 dated 20.05.2022 "On measures to organize the cultural cultivation and processing of medicinal plants and their widespread use in treatment" was adopted.

Medicinal plants are plants used for the treatment of humans and animals, the prevention of diseases, as well as in the food, perfumery and cosmetic industries. There are 10-12 thousand species of medicinal plants on Earth. The chemical and pharmacological properties of more than 1,000 plant species have been investigated. There are more than 700 species of medicinal plants in Uzbekistan. Of these, about 120 species of plants growing in natural conditions and cultivated are used in scientific and folk medicine. Currently, about 40-47%

of medicines used in medicine are obtained from plant raw materials. Plants are a living natural chemical laboratory with a complex structure, capable of creating complex organic substances or compounds from simple inorganic substances. The dried herb, bud, root, rhizome, tuber, bulb, bark, leaf, flower, bud, fruit (seed), seed, juice, decoction, tea, essential oils, etc. of medicinal plants are used as medicine.

Literature Review

Previous studies on the Allium motor plant, “Allium hydrocarbons. Polysaccharides from Allium motor”, the dependence of the carbohydrate content in Allium motor on the vegetation period were studied.

In the study of authentication of medicinal herbs using multispectral analysis, the technologies of drying Allium motor plants were studied.

Information is provided about the unique, unique, medicinal properties of Allium motor plants.

The chemical composition of Allium motor plants and its beneficial properties for human health.[1-3]

Research methods

The Parkent region of Uzbekistan and the Chatkal mountain range and the adjacent Kyrgyz and Kazakh regions are included. Allium motor plant belongs to the onion family. There are many types of them. They bloom and bloom in the spring months of April and May. The motor plant is a medicinal plant that contains several types of vitamins. The leaves of the motor plant are dried and then extracted.

<Chromatogram>

mAU

Figure 1 Chromatogram of standard samples of vitamins B1, B2, B6, B9, B12, C and PP

The qualitative and quantitative parameters of vitamins B1 (47858), B2 (47864), B6 (80823-50MG), Vitamin B9 (PHR1035-1G), B12 (PHR1234-1), C (47863) and PP (47865-U) in the finely ground samples were determined based on standard samples from Sigma Aldrich Germany using a YSSX LC 2030 C 3D Plus device manufactured in Japan (Shimadzu) with a PDA detector at wavelengths of 260, 290 and 361 nm. A C18 250x4.6 mm 5 µm Precise (Perkin Elmer) USA column was used as the stationary phase.

RESULTS

As a result of the experiments, the main weather conditions affecting the efficiency of the solar panel were analyzed using a 0.5% solution of acetic acid as the mobile phase and acetonitrile as the mobile phase in an alternating mode.

Table 1

Time is minute	Phase A %0.5% solution of acetic acid in water	Phase B % Acetonitrile
0,1	96	4
4	90	10
8	85	15
12	60	40

The flow rate was 1 ml/min, the thermostat temperature was 400C, the injected sample volume was 10 µl, the analysis time was 14 minutes, and the chromatograms were obtained as follows.

Table 2

	Vitamin B ₁ (mg/100g)	Vitamin B ₂ (mg/100g)	Vitamin B ₆ (mg/100g)	Vitamin B ₁₂ (mg/100g)	Vitamin B ₉ (mg/100g)	Vitamin PP (mg/100g)	Vitamin C (mg/100g)
Plant sample	73,117	42,236	45,421	19,040	11,976	223,262	39,621

Discussion

The extraction of vitamins from the sample is carried out as follows: 1 g of the sample (FA220 4N) was weighed with an accuracy of 0.001 mg on an analytical balance. Then, 20 ml of 0.1 N hydrochloric acid solution was added and mixed on a magnetic stirrer for 60 min at room temperature. The resulting

solution was centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 10 min and filtered through a 0.45 µm filter and placed in a vial, and the following results were obtained.

Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above studies:

1. Allium motor is a medicinal plant and is rich in vitamins.
2. Vitamins necessary and beneficial for human organisms can be provided by consuming natural plants.
3. The results of thermal analysis of the above samples are consistent with the results of chemical analysis.

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